

Araştırma Makalesi

Doi:

China's Economic Effects on East African Countries*

Abdiwahab MOHAMED HASSAN¹, Dr. Yunus ÖZCAN²

Başvuru Tarihi:11.08.2021

Kabul Tarihi: 21.08.2021

Yayın Tarihi:25.09.2021

ABSTRACT

China-Africa trade in 2018 was \$113bn but dropped due to pandemic and it hit \$108bn in 2020 while China's imports from Africa was \$71.6bn in 2020. In the East African communities, the leading export country is Tanzania with \$144.59m in 2020 tailed by Kenya and Uganda, but the other side the biggest consumer is Kenya which is \$3.39b tailed by Tanzania and Uganda. It seems that Chinese engagement in Africa is to establish and shape the future of African countries in contrary Chinese firms. Their workers travelled to Africa and make harsh competitions while China was providing the top investments in Africa. Africa has attained close to \$30bn from China in the annual basis for the source of infrastructures being the management of projects and the financing. Regardless of the fact many African countries praise these funds, while others worry the range of the funds. This paper tries to analyze trade impact of Chinese support in a form of aid and investments that keep in the main values of strategic diplomacy, ideological values and commercial gains that include China involvement in the African continent.

Keywords: *East African Economies, Chinese Economy, International Trade*

ÇİN'İN DOĞU AFRIKA ÜLKELERİ ÜZERİNDEKİ EKONOMİK ETKİLERİ

ÖZET

Çin-Afrika ticareti 2018'de 113 milyar olarak gerçekleşmiş ve pandemi nedeniyle 2020'de 108 milyar dolara kadar düşmüştür. Çin'in Afrika'dan ithalatı 2020'de 71.6 milyar dolar olarak gerçekleşmiştir. Doğu Afrika topluluklarında, önde gelen ihracat ülkesi 2020'de 144.59 milyon dolar ile Kenya ve Uganda'nın önünde Tanzanya'dır. Ancak en büyük tüketici, Tanzanya ve Uganda tarafından takip edilen 3,39 milyar dolar ile Kenya'dır. Görünen o ki, Çin'in Afrika'daki angajmanı Çin firmalarının aksine Afrika ülkelerinin geleceğini kurmak ve şekillendirmek içindir. Çin, Afrika'daki en büyük yatırımları sağlarken Çinli firmalar yüksek rekabet göstermişlerdir. Afrika projelerin yönetimi ve finansmanı olan altyapı yatırımları için kaynağı için yıllık 30 Milyar ABD Dolarına yakın bir yatırım almaktadır. Birçok Afrika ülkesi bu fonları överken, diğerleri fonların çeşitliliğinden endişe etmektedir. Bu makale, Çin'in Afrika kıtasına katılımını içeren stratejik diplomasi, ideolojik değerler ve ticari kazanımların ana değerlerini koruyan bir yardım ve yatırım biçiminde Çin desteğinin ticari etkisini analiz etmeye çalışmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Doğu Afrika Ekonomileri, Çin Ekonomisi, Uluslararası Ticaret*

* Bu çalışma Yüksek Lisans tezinden türetilmiştir.

¹ İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi, Dış Ticaret Enstitüsü, Uluslararası Ticaret Yüksek Lisans Programı Öğrencisi; faarax17@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-2390-5422

² İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi, İşletme Fakültesi, İktisat Bölümü Öğretim Üyesi; yozcan@ticaret.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0001-7895-0194

1. Introduction

The world image for Chinese support in the countries is provided through aid and investments that keep in the main values of strategic diplomacy, ideological values and commercial gains that include China involvement in the African continent that show images for the reasoning in the significant values for recognition of the forgotten issues in the discussion of the relationships. The China is facing the partners in the broad diplomacy for the tight African countries that have become for the many targets. China is needed for the countries that take recognition of China as the instance of the stands through China that come through rejections of the society. Furthermore, the coming of ideas and values for China was to involve the Africa in the most effect for the own developed focus on experiences in growth. China goes through a change in economic transformed way for the simple agreements in projecting the ideas that come for the economic transformed form for involvement in African governments.

China provided an attraction to Africa for the early measure Tang dynasty (AD. 618-907). For the 19th century reporting in the trade of meat, ivory exportation from modern Kenya and Tanzania confirming the provided avenues Kaplinsky, McCormick and Morris (2007). The China Africa relations has provided enrichment for the intellect in a cultural and commercial but provided for issues in the China promise for the movement for economic development and fighting poverty than in the western nations for development. Diplomacy in China is provided in the embassies for 44 African nations. The conceptual available for the study in China African environment that explain the occurrence of trade relations among the countries.

China and Africa share a reliance that can be seen in the third year of Beijing summit for the China-Africa cooperation forum. In 2006 for the summit included for the state official, leaders for the representations for the 40 African countries, the former Chinese President Jiang Zemin toured Africa four times. For the 2007, President Hu Jintao had paid visit for the 5th time for the continent in a twice formed measure in the vice president and 3 times as president. China is providing a flexible means to economic management in Africa due to the needs for colonization of Africa due to the mercantilist ambitions for natural resources such as petroleum, timber, cobalt, platinum, cooper, diamond etc. Alden (2009) argued that Chinese going through the engagements in enabling the shaping of the future of the African continent.

China is now one of the African economic impacts in Africa's core trading partners. for recent years, a million of Chinese have travelled to Africa for the reliable expand mechanism of growth (Pere, 2013). The status of the African continent and institutional developments among the countries provided in the means to generate efficiency in trade supported by the Chinese economies. The example for the expansion includes the new hospital and school for the Angola the railway for the projects such as Kenya (Onjala, 2014). The construction for the Africa union in Addis Ababa and energy extractions for Tanzania. China government and its companies have a significant increase in presence of the continent focus in Africa for the past 2 decades. China has become the main trade pattern for Africa (Sun, 2014).

China economy experiences the sporadic change in the growth over the 2 decades that has an effect on the world economic forum for search and abundance in the resources for satisfying the demands in industrials countries. The provided is due to the domestic needs in the Chinese having the look for the broad resources in satisfaction in the ever-changing demands. The last decade China demand has managed for creation of the aid in investments connected to the 50 African nations (Luong& Sierra 2013). China has led a building force in the relations assessment for countries. The overall few years in supporting of the influence for China that increased marked forms to the continent. The nations have provided African large trading partners in the joint form of improvement in a drastic raise for the heights to \$166.3 billion.

The estimates for 800 Chinese firms in Africa for the energy, infrastructures in banking developed forum China-Africa cooperation. The ministry conferences for the FOCAC that was 200 that are recent the holding of the people in management (Sutter, Robert, 2015). Chinese- Africa relations characters in the summit for diplomacy for the equal development in cooperation for the worth in the maintaining for the summits in diplomacy that for the development in cooperative forms worth the summit diplomacy established in the country with exception of the country. Rotberg (2015) contend that China for the different forms of policies for the embodiment in the principles of not inferring in the issues of countries.

The African countries has provided a retained form of the same intervention in the adoption of the domestic international conditions. The China engagement for Africa for the chances of the African situations in the emergence of the provided reasonable for developing a means to development in a national and equal focus measure for development in international relations for the countries. The continuity of the invested form of capital flow for the countries. China has provided the top investments in Africa. China has provided the investments in Africa for the studies in the Chinese vested forms that has provided several attack forms (Li Xing 2010). The last decade provided an avenue in the apparent form of China investments for the case of policy and driving the domestic development strategy (Zweig and Jianhai 2005). Africa has attained close to US\$30 Billion in the annual basis for the source of infrastructures being the management of projects based on China and the financing.

Regardless of the fact many Africa praise the fund and knowledge, while others worry the range of the funds, China is moving with heavy boots. This heavy movement has sparked a question about whether China carries opportunity or challenges with urbanized nations and huge world contributors. On such conflicts this thesis therefore examined Chinas partnership whit African countries especial East African Communities. This study aims to investigate if African interaction is a factor in developing countries position in economic growth. It is intended to gather a lesson from China and influencing the economic patterns policies of East Africa toward the international expansion.

2. East African Community

The resolution which forming the East African community was reached at on 3 November 1999 and agreement was reached on 7th July 2000 after the ratification of the initial three original partner member states of Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda and after accession Rwanda and Burundi to the community, the agreement was reached on 18th June 2007, and 1 July 2007 become member of the community. South Sudan also applied on 15th April 2016 and became full member on 15th August 2016 (EAC, 2016). The main objective for the community was implementation of the policy and program to foster cooperation among the members for the achievement of benefits in the vast range attained that include political, economic, social and culture aspects in the research and innovations, safety and constitutional plus judiciary situation.

In March 2004, the East African community member state has signed Custom treaties in order to create standard external tariff for imports from third parties and to phase out tariffs. The procedure for the goods entry into force in January 2005 and step by step procedure for the implementation of customs union which was successfully finished in January 2010. The implementation of custom union has contributed significantly to the removal of some of trade barriers, though other challenges still exist. The non-harmonized regulatory sanitary and phytosanitary techniques required customs procedures, records, laws and regulations to block the key barriers to trade in the East African community. Customs union treaty was accompanied by the signing of the protocol resulted in the creation of the EAC common market in November 2009. In July 2010, the Common Market came into effect. The changes for concentrate from the exclusively liberal goods and tariffs for the further unrestricted movement of the goods and or services including labour and capital.

In combination for GDP in 2019 for Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, the Tanzania, South Sudan and Uganda was measured at US\$ 193.7 Billion and the population for the EAC membership states was 177 million at 2019. Africa is growing in performance and has been better in the many other regions around the globe with the exception of the East Asia (5.6% on average in 2015) that has been better in the regions around the world with exception of the East and South Asia even with the negative effects in the 2008-2009 for the globe economics (UNECA, 2016). The growing form for performance in East Africa countries that was also above the world averages with though the growth falling into 2.6% in 2015 (EAC, 2016).

This section can be divided into subheadings. It should provide a brief and precise description of the experimental results, their interpretation and the experimental results that can be drawn.

2.1 Burundi Economy

Burundi is one of East Africa's lowest economies and has a sluggish growth (AfDB, 2014). Burundi's civil war continued from 1993 to 2005 and concluded in 2005, securing representation for the parliamentary elections of the Hutu and Tutsi. Political tensions were related to the presidential election in 2015. Outcomes of the Policy Crisis Report in Burundi Economies Reducing Economic Crisis Reducing GDP in 2015.

The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic in Burundi dropped into recession in 2020. After increasing by 4.1% in 2019, the real GDP dropped by 3.3%. The pandemic affected the industry, with output and services decreasing by 4.5 percent compared to 2019, whose output decreased by 1.8 percent. Investment has decreased by around 3 percent on the demand side. A decrease in agricultural production and the rise in import prices have led to a significant spike in pricing. Inflation in 2020 increased by 8.5 points to 7.6% compared to -0.7% in 2019. The budget deficit increased by around 4% to 8.7% of GDP by 2020, compared to 4.2 percent in 2019.

Due to a poor worldwide demand, prices of coffee exports decreased 4,4 percent and tea deficits deteriorated 10,4%. The present account deficit stood at 19.1% of GDP, up from 17.8% in 2019. This resulted in a decline in foreign currency reserves, which by the end of 2020 may be fewer than 30 days of imports. Between May 2019 and May 2020, the exchange rate between the Burundian franc and the US dollar dropped 3.8%.

Burundi's governmental debt has increased rapidly since 2015, and is 70% domestic, when civil instability led to a dry outage of external financing. Public debt accounts for around 63.7% of GDP by 2020. External debt is 18.4% of GDP in 2020 when the conditions for complete debt relieve available under the Highly Indebted Poor Countries program were fulfilled, compared to 36% in 2012 when Burundi was (HIPC). Burundi's risk of financial distress is high due to the chronic trade imbalance and continuing

increase in national debt due to the sustained budget deficits. A major public debt objective is to undertake a comprehensive public finance reform to achieve a balanced budget over time.

Figure 1: Burundi Economic Developments and Projections: 2019-2022

Source: African Economic Outlook (AEO) 2021

2.2 Uganda Economy

Even if Uganda's economy has been increasing dramatically, the world and Africa have been growing on balance since the 2000s, the nation has been behind Rwanda and Tanzania in performance growth since the 1990. Uganda's demographic pressure is one of several stated in Africa, and the nation wants financial capital for health care deductions, and institutional structures are linked to another major hustle. The non-favorable market atmosphere available is thus negatively impacting the private sector. In order to attain the value chain, the agricultural sector needs to be enforced and action taken. (UNECA, 2015d).

In the first quarter, Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) data for the economy increased by 6.4 percent on year. for FY 18/19, continuous focus on the same moments for the last quarter of FY17/18, the major improved form for 4.5% in growth realized in the first quarter for FY 17/18. Government is projecting the economic growth for 6.2% for the FY 2018/19. The estimated mode of the Ministry of Finance in December 2018 throughout the National Budgets Process Paper 2019/20.

Uganda's economy was affected by the COVID-19 and its following lockdowns to prevent the spread of the virus. In 2020, real GDP dropped by 0.5% and by 7.5% in 2019. Global travel bans and local containment efforts have seriously affected tourism and hospitality. Manufacturing, retail, wholesale and education are among industries affected severely. The Bank of Uganda cut the policy rate to 8% in April and subsequently to 7% in June to stimulate companies.

Nonetheless, inflation remained significantly below the 5% medium-term objective of the central bank at 3.8%. As government spending on public health, including enhanced testing and cross-border monitoring of COVID-19 rose in 2020, the fiscal deficit grew from 5.2 percent in 2019 to 6.6 percent in 2020. The government also gave corporate help, although the economy in general remained weak and reduced tax receipts. In order to address income gap, government borrowing rose. The debt-to-GDP ratio increased from 35.9% a year before to 40.8% in June 2020. As a result of the reduction in economic activity, the banking sector has suffered growing pressure. Non-performing loans increased as lending to the private sector slowed down. Lending that was not performing grew from 3.8% a year earlier to 6.0% of gross credits in 2019-20. Credit expansion increased by 8%, from May to October 2018 to May 2019, compared to 15%.

The progress in the sector is continued for recovery in agriculture that has large benefits for favorable conditions is current major drivers for economic recorded in the 1.2% increased growth for the quarter of the up from 0.6 growth mentioned in the first quarter. The improvement in the agriculture zone for exports provided in the major boosts for the economy (Ali, Deininger and Duponchel, 2016). The base for many data in the economy is provided in the both BOU and ministry for finance that is providing the key developments for the national development targets. The government is hence in need for urgency in coming up with the economic growth that is ensuring the Ugandans in unemployed form for Youth feel the effect for the growth in the economies of the country. The continued weak current account positioning result in the high imports for the growth of the resulting depreciations for the shillings. The renewed exchange rate instability for the shillings that provide a bad environment for the economic and inflation environments that can defeat the consumer demand rise in the prices for import of goods. the optimistic economic outlook could be influenced by a variety of external and internal threats. External threats include low commodity prices for the country's export demand as a result of a substantial market appreciation for the US dollar due to the anticipated increase in US interest rates.

The internal risk to economies includes a decrease in domestic revenue mobilization, high contingency expenditure and poor institutional governance growth, plus weak management of public financial systems. The agricultural sector is vulnerable to adverse China's Economic Effects on East African Countries, 2021

weather conditions because of the remaining economic risks. The government with a continued failure in meeting the budget target for the under executed form of development in the budgets for concerns. Low GDP per capita under provides that unemployment and growth in population is an increase for planned rural urban migrations that support the projection of the Ugandans as being poor.

Figure 2: The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Uganda

Source: tradingeconomics.com

According to the United Nations COMTRADE international trade statistics repository, Uganda imports from China amounted to \$1.35 trillion for 2020. The previous update was made on July of 2021 for Uganda imported from China. According to the United Nations COMTRADE database on international commerce, Uganda's exports to China amounted to US\$ 39,61 million for 2020. The recent updates on Uganda exports to China were made in July 2021.

2.3 Tanzania Economy

Tanzania has tried to hold peaceful elections from the start of multiparty democracy in 1992 and is taken as apolitically stable country. Tanzania performs a fundamental role in the landlocked countries neighboring it and serves as the sea port and transport corridor systems facilitations. (AfDB, 2014). Furthermore, Tanzania is among the fastest economies with high growth in East Africa, despite the impressive performance growth the country has a series of vulnerabilities such as the minerals that are key as a share for export and country suffers reductions/ fluctuations in prices in their commodities (UNECA, 2015c).

Figure 3: The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Tanzania

Source: tradingeconomics.com

reached 1.4 Percent for GDP lower than the budgeted target for 15.5%. The expenditures were low for 16.9% for GDP is low expected in capital expenditures. The 2019/20 tax collection increased from 15.5% on the GDP for the expenditure expected driven with the increased in goods expenditures for the capital goods. The public debt is current in sustainable in the low risks for the debts in the recent in the debt sustainable analysis (Wodon and Brière, 2018).

High frequency official data indicate that the scale of economic activities given in 2018 was claimed by the Tanzania Central Statistical Bureau that GDP growth in 2018 was 7% higher than 6.8% in 2017. The official demand, including the related investment consumption and the target indicating 2018 growth, is the official demand. Tanzania's revenue authority, which shows low consumption in tax collection, offers soft consumption in growth with strict controls for public expenditures. Investing in growth is a dampened need demonstrated by substantial public development planning performed, Low FDI degree and the development of the nominal credit of the private sector. In 2018, trade balances declined in export contractions by 3.9 percent in gross import prices, rising to 7.8 percent in 2018. (Onagoruwaand Wodon, 2018).

A rising current account deficit and declining reserves threaten the external situation. The amount of the exports given dropped due to low cash exports and imports resulting from the supply growth project leading to capital goods. In the 12 months, the account deficit rose to 5.2 percent of GDP in January 2019, to 3.2 percent a year before. Low foreign exchange flows for exports and FDI gross reserves deficit finance aid dropped from US\$5.8 billion to 4.9 billion in 2018 are therefore sufficient to support the 4.8 months of imports of goods and services. The shilling has remained flat in the foreign exchange control offices due to banking initiatives in Tanzania for the interbank foreign exchange markets.

According to the UN COMTRADE database on international commerce, Tanzania imports from China amounted to US\$1.77 billion for 2018. Tanzania Chinese imports – data, were last updated in July 2021. According to the UN COMTRADE database on international commerce, Tanzania's exports to China amounted to \$144.59 million in 2018. Last updated in July of 2021 was the export of Tanzania to China.

Figure 4: Tanzania Export to China

Source: tradingeconomics.com

2.4 Kenya Economy

Kenya is indeed one of the largest economies in the economies for the East Africa Communities for the only concentrated in the members in favorable geographic position good economic conditions in infrastructures linked strong compared to the neighbors. For many decades, Kenya has faced the constraints of structural changes in terms of production, exports and jobs (UNECA, 2015a). Throughout the presence of political and social economic vulnerability, Kenya is not seen as a country of African growth due, among other factors, to political, ethnic and limited devotion to low horizons. (AfDB, 2014).

Figure 5: The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Kenya

Source: tradingeconomics.com

Kenya economy performed well in 2018 and the economic activity in the 1st quarter of 2019 it was health despite the emergence of drought conditions in the country that curtailed GDP for the remaining part of the year. The economic expansion increased by 6% in the 1st quarter of 2018 as compared to 4.7% in the same period provided strong consumptions for the case of improving the incomes for investments in agriculture in 2018, flow of the cash remittance and food prices. The bank GDP growing at an estimated form of 2018 in 5.8%, the increase in the economy activity was raised in 2019 provided a reflection of the growth in the consumer expenditures providing strong investment sentiments. The ongoing emergencies in intervention for food shortages count could reduce fiscal pressures in capital expenses that hinder the development and slow down the forecast in 2019 for the medium-term relative to the October environment of 2018.

The current account deficit reduced in 2018 and remains adequate financing. The 2018 current deficits reduced to 4.9% for GDP due to strong Diaspora remittance flows, improving the exports for the tea and horticulture and providing a strong Diaspora remittance through exports in tea, horticulture and strong Diaspora remittance tourisms. The current deficits continue for adequate for resilient for capital governance in 9.3% increased for official reserves for relative to 2017. The continuation for the buffer against external short-term shocks.

The fiscal consolidation has halted the rapid rise in the stock for the public debts, the underperformance in revenues for the fiscal deficits reduced for the 6.8% for the financial year 2017/18 from 8.8% of the GDP in FY 2016/17 due for values in contradictions in the development expenses for the marginal decreases in the recurrent expenses. The result for the public debts remains for about 57.5% percentage of the GDP in 2018 half of the rapid accumulated form of the beginning in the FY 2012/13. The FY 2018/19 for the fiscal deficit for projection in decreased form further for decreased form of 6.3% to GDP, the recent turn in revenue collected and expenditure fall in the below target due for the budget implanted that lead to ramp in expenses for the fiscal year that has damage for pressure in public finance resources.

The medium growth look is stable in the recent threats for drought that can drag the GDP, the GDP growth is a projection of 5.7% in 2019 rising the 5.9 and 6% respectively in 2020 for 2021 support in the private consumptions for the industrial activities and strong performance for the services sector. Inflation expected in remaining the government struggle target range in the services for the sectors. Inflation is an expectation remains with the government for target range while for the current deficit to project remaining the managing.

The macro-economic environment remaining the broad stable in the inflation remaining in the government target bond for 2.5%. the inflation reduced to average of rate of 4.4% in 2018 low compared to the food prices for the effects rising oil prices result in begin inflation. The provision for the policy in space for the purpose of accommodation monetary stances in supporting the growth. 4.3% percent in August 2018 for the private credit growth remaining sub-deed in the historical information percentage. The Notwithstanding recent surge for the oil price for the current account deficit for a narrow form in 6.7% in 2017 for 5.3% in July. The adequate form of finance is surplus for the results accommodating the official foreign reserves for the 5.6 Months for the cover in September 2018.

Growth in the projection remains strong in the medium terms with the GDP expectation rising to be 5.8% in 2019 and 6% for 2020. The raise in the increase is determined by the current reduction in the economic status for the gasps expected in a close for the medium terms. The growing forecast is enabled by the expected recovery in agriculture and demand domestically. The external balances positions are also remained large for the consistent in the April 2018 economic update in the reduction in the reversions

for the percentage in 2019 and 2020. Growing the high in absence for interests in the environment remaining tied for the policy rate hence reducing or hindering effective money policy affecting the private sector and the credit sector for management in the economies.

According to the United Nations COMTRADE Database on international commerce, Kenya's exports to China amounted to US\$139.01 million by 2020. The most updated export of Kenya to China was made in July 2021 - facts, historical chart & statistics. According to UN COMTRADE's international trade database, Kenya imports from China amounted to US\$3.39 billion for 2020. The recent updating of Chinese exports from Kenya was made in July 2021.

Figure 6: Kenya Imports from China

Source: tradingeconomics.com

3. History of Relationship Between China and East African Countries

In understanding early bond between the two continents, postcolonial relationships between China and Africa have revived interest. As early as Shang (Yin) times, African domesticates such as millet and sorghum were domesticated in Asia, while Asian domesticates such as bananas and rice made their way to Africa early on. No geological evidence remains, however, for more direct interaction between East Africa and China. Communication at this stage was mostly thought to be more indirect, by overland trade and migration through the Eurasian steppes, the same route used by African primates in the initial migrations from Africa. In more recent times, Connections between East Africa and China have been more common since the Tang Dynasty (c. AD 618-907).

From the Tang through Qing Dynasties (ca. AD 618-1912), the continuous occurrence of Chinese trade ceramics in dateable archaeological contexts at many major places in East Africa points to a long, fruitful relationship between China and East Africa. Reports on ancient Chinese ceramics excavated at historical sites in Kenya are explored in this chapter and the potential of the long-term collaborative research agenda on ancient and contemporary ties between China and East Africa. Research from both archaeological and historical sources has revealed over the past five decades that cultural growth on the eastern coast of Africa is closely related to the production of complexly structured merchant towns, the procurement of ship-borne goods from the far corners of the globe and the sending of products from the interior of Africa (Kusimba 1999: 2).

From the very early days of recorded time, the coastal region of East Africa played a prominent role in world history. It was the bridge on which the first Africans deserted the continent in ancient times to venture east and colonize the world. In historical times, the north, the coasts of Somalia. The caravan pathways connecting to the Nile Valley through all these famed towns as the secret town of Harar were offered. The people and goods of the Great Lakes area in the Highlands are connected to the markets of Zanzibar and the island archipelagos by their central ranges in Kenya and Tanzania. Throughout the south, with the slopes of Zambezia, docks along the Mozambique Gulf trafficked inland and the precious wealth dominated by the Shona kingdoms governed from massive cities like Great Zimbabwe (Kusimba, Nam, and Kusimba, 2017).

The east coast of Africa was scattered with the traces of this ancient civilization until the 1980s: the remains of once-flourishing towns with their affluent palaces and coral-rag mosques. These notable sites were built around 500 to 1200 years ago by ancestors of the current coastal peoples. Their ideology was traditionally Islamic, and generations of economic interaction and conquest from southern Arabia, western India, and Portugal impacted them and changed them (Pearson, 2003).

Internal and external ties with populations as far as Indonesia and China are involved likely to have been developed early on China's Economic Effects on East African Countries, 2021

following the successful settlement in Madagascar of the Austronesians. Yet, amid this welter of external interactions, archaeological and anthropological research basically seeking to understand historical transcontinental communication between Africa and Eurasia is still in adolescence. It was a culture that remained fundamentally African. Subaltern scholarship attempts to fill the vacuum have engaged callously in silencing Africa from the discussion (Abu-Lughod, 2008). For centuries, Africa and Asia have experienced developments in cultural, economic and technical terms. Several of the food production in most of sub-Saharan Africa that are now staple foods were first played with and domesticated in Asia. Some of the African pastoral nomads, such as sorghum, millet, coffee, are generally served as staples by modern Asians. (Shipton et al., 2016).

The various archaeological remains that have been recovered at many sites across the continent show ancient ties between Africa and Asia, including China (e.g. Horton and Middleton 2000). Indo-Pacific beads, glass, glazed pottery and jewelry from the Middle East, artifacts, Chinese stoneware and porcelain, among others, were recovered from the Tang Dynasty to the present in almost all reasonable sized towns in the Eastern and Southern African subcontinent (Wilson 2016). This non-African materiality is a reference to global ties, The accomplishments and difficulty of the past of Africa systematically disregards the long-held narrative that Africa was isolated from Eurasia and amounted precious little to global civilization apart from North Africa.

3.1 The Role of Islam in Linking China and East Africa

The attribution is to Prophet Mohamed seeking to create awareness in China, laying the foundations for evaluating China's importance in global trade in the times of the Western Indian Ocean and South Western Asia. The memorial mosque is the first mosque in China created in the orders of the Emperor Yong Hui in 651 where the mosque is then still standing until today providing the early evidence for formal Islam in China. The ancient time for the two routes is connected to China in the ancient time for the two routes connected to western Asia and Africa routes in Asia and western Asia routes passing through the China sea and Indian Ocean ways for Indonesia, Sri Lanka and Persian Gulf (Horton 1996:307).

3.2 Global Connections: China and Africa

Trade offers a fundamental role in the growth of cultures since ancient times to facilitate contact between trade and different individuals in the community network that has a high impact on the progress of everyday life. Archaeology and history have provided evidence in the fields of biological culture, language, commercial and technical communication in the middle of east Africa and Middle East starting with the early millennium chief executives. The boundary of the third century supposes that the iron lances, hatchets, daggers and awls produced in the east of Aden constitute the trade in the markets' shipments. In India and the Middle East of China, trade articles for East African consigned market type, including marine products in animal products such as horns and cats for vegetable products, mangrove poles and timber. The shells and ambergris are in demand for ivory horns and leopard skins exported from India and China via the Persian Gulf of India and China (Yulvisaker 1982). Timber construction is an aromatic product that is needed in relatively recent forms for the Persian Gulf. The market for African timber in the Gulf has a sufficiently high report for Ibn Hawqal, 960 House Chief Executive built in the wood for the country in jinjs.

In Mogadishu with the Manda, Zanzibar, Kilwa and Mahilaka, the manufacturing industry in silk and cotton produced in other towns experiencing trade in East Africa that enter the far Egypt. The Portuguese visits were greatly impressed by the high quality of production, the mining and working iron industry in Malindi and other towns were of good value The standard of iron products produced in East Africa is exceptional for the additions offered in Africa and Indian scales for frequent merchants visiting the coast with the annual monsoon winds (Horton 1996:418). For 912 CE, historians like Al Masudi visited the East African society, leaving one in the cogent forms mentioned for the industry on the coast for coast for the meadows of the gold and mines in Gems.

The start of the second millennium of East African, Southern provided that more Africa had to become regular in the partnership for the old distance exchanges reached for the far in the Arabia, peninsula, India, Sri Lanka and China (Wilkinson 2003). The 13th century provided an emergency of the local African urban cities that finance the management and control of the local, regional economic trade in oceans alongside the east African community. Innovation in work aide agriculture intensified and specialization for the hunt in fishing. Changes improve the quality for the precipitate the population in economic determined forms for 200 years.

3.3 China Policy on Eastern Africa

China's Eastern Africa policy is not merely aimed at protecting Chinese economic and security interests. Beijing also focuses on providing development and stability that benefit local communities. This article addresses the question how China reconciles the dilemmas arising from potentially conflicting demands from China's foreign policy doctrines and the overseas context in which Chinese policies are implemented. For example, Beijing's support for an African security architecture to promote security and stability as a basis for development creates dilemmas for China. Regional forums, such as the African Union (AU), demand more robust and offensive United Nation (UN) operations. Such demands clash with China's preference for a defensive security posture based on strict adherence to non-interference (Odgaard, 2012).

The policy of non-interference has allowed China to establish a global economic engagement irrespective of political, social or economic differences with recipient countries. Beijing's answer to these dilemmas is to become increasingly engaged in designing and providing for regional order and economic development. Regional order is made up of fundamental rules of conduct which benefit the mutual interest of states in peace and security. China's approach to East African order: OBOR and the UN combined effectively, China's OBOR initiative is a grand plan to connect 4.4 billion citizens and more than 60 countries from Beijing to Europe, via Central Asia, the Middle East and Africa, in a modern version of the Silk Roads land and sea. The project is to establish China at the center of a global interconnection network OBOR is focused on Chinese governance principles that are negotiated in collaboration with partner countries and as the project unfolds.

OBOR is one of the major projects of China's Xi Jinping administration (Guidetti, 2015). The main goal of OBOR is to create an alternative to the liberal free trade projects of Western states and institutions, or in the least, to conform to neoliberalism with 'Chinese characteristics. This alternative includes technology sharing, frequent demands for compulsory partnerships between foreign and domestic actors, strong state-owned companies, and tight capital control. Further goals include the growth of China's overseas markets and the rise in Chinese energy supply sources.

In contrast, an important aim involves fostering financial stability by developing standards of behaviour at a time when China is initially appeared to financial risk. OBOR includes projects powered by private markets and economic development projects. The East African part of OBOR is governed by the latter type. The stability goal is crucial to China's willingness to devote capital to projects which may not be economically feasible.

OBOR has been blamed for not providing a consistent system of regulations to lead its operations and illustrate to other states its intent, priorities and tools. This may be true. For example, the absence of clear rules is strategically useful since it allows Beijing to adopt flexible approaches depending on local and historical conditions. Other opinions have suggested that OBOR is a term for existing projects rather than an effort to develop great new projects. For example, in East Africa, a number of port and rail projects were agreed before the announcement of OBOR, and both pre- and post-OBOR projects are established by a mixture of state-owned and private companies; however, labelling matters as an 'OBOR initiative' creates the sense that China is responsible for contributing to economic growth and development.

China has hooked up with the UN system in its pursuit of gradual revisions to the existing principles concerning global development and security management. For example, China acknowledges the UN-based Responsibility to Protect (R2P) doctrine on the responsibility to protect populations against atrocity crimes. However, China challenges Western efforts to use the doctrine to legalise the right to intervene without regime consent. Beijing insists that implementation of R2P begins with the responsibility of the state in which atrocity crimes are committed and pursues this interpretation when engaged in peace and stability efforts in states such as South Sudan (Alessi & Xu, 2016).

This way of going about exercising influence has several advantages. If China embedded its overseas activities in Sino-centric concepts of world order, Beijing would meet immediate resistance to policies and principles of conduct that have no a priority legitimacy with other states. By contrast, the UN system has universal legitimacy, so China only has to persuade the international community this its interpretation of right and wrong conduct is in compliance with the UN Charter. On this basis, China has successfully defended the status of absolute sovereignty and introduced its own policy on how to pursue development and security overseas.

China emphasizes the importance of the UN in efforts to safeguard African peace and stability. China's approach to regional order is to use the continent-wide forum of the AU as a flexible platform for policy coordination with Africa as a whole to facilitate bilateral agreements outside of the AU framework. Even when China dispatched a permanent mission to the AU in 2015, China primarily collaborated with African countries' ambassadors, signaling that China's strategy is not consistent with the AU.

Consequently, most of China's East African projects are bilateral intergovernmental or private sector projects. However, while bolstering China's reputation as a responsible great power, such involvement and support of regional security architecture also bears the risk of creating a situation in which China will be confronted with its reluctance to support interference in other states' sovereign sphere. This could have been the case with Burundi in 2016 if the collective AU had supported an intervention without the consent of Burundi's government, placing China in a difficult dilemma (Sun, 2017).

4. China Investment in East African Communities: Advantages and Disadvantages

Another key problem is that the diversification of these East African economies from rough agricultural and mineral items to production and, eventually, to services or knowledge-intensive sectors may be discouraged in actuality by cheap Chinese imports.

This is a genuine problem since it may be undesirable for new investors to compete or not to compete for cheap Chinese imports, because Chinese imports are so high that no meaningful surplus demand can aspire to be met. In this scenario, instead of giving aid to the process of change and evolution in East Africa to the Sino-African economic relationship, in fact, it's going to truncate. This will in fact reverse the benefits of industrial growth in Africa, together with the deindustrialization impacts of cheap Chinese imports, in the course of two decades of independence.

Africa has been more violent than any other continent in the previous decades. These disputes have occurred mostly in Angola, the DRC, Sierra Leone and Sudan, which have huge natural resources, including oil and mineral resources. The major source of conflict was mainly how these resources may be controlled. Peace and stability in many countries have begun to reign, but in certain areas- The major impediment to growth remains, as is the case in Sudan, a deadly war. Chinese trade partnership oil profits may also be used by some of these nations to support dictators, impede transparency in trade transactions, fuel wars, and abuses of human rights in Africa (Lyakurwa, 2006). These disputes are typically the cause of deepening poverty for the poor. The difficulty lies in preventing escalation of violence and social-political instability for the African leaders. No overemphasis may be placed on the instrumentality of the African Peer Review Mechanism (APRM).

Foreign oil, mining and other resource industry firms need to increase public scrutiny of their payments. African countries exporting oil and minerals should continue to implement the rule of law, reducing corruption and the pursuit of rents so that oil and mineral money can contribute to economic progress. This is the road of nations such as Botswana that have adopted these policies and achieved economic development, growth and poverty reduction (Olomola, 2005). The problem is for East African governments to demand on these international firms which subscribe to the EITI (Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative) as a prerequisite for grants.

Trade in Chances The biggest potential offered by China's growing prominence in international commerce may be the introduction of an additional cycle of commodity booms due to increasing demand for mineral and agricultural raw materials. While it is not completely due to China's increasing role in the international economy that the continuing commodities boom is, it can be denied that it has at least increased it.

The comparability of its conditions with IDA credit facilities without political conditionality is a great potential offered by China's aid in Africa. China requires the compliance of one-China policy instead of the normal policy conditionality. Countries that desire Chinese help should thus be ready to engage in harsh diplomatic contacts with Taiwan. Essentially, the rise in demand for and the prices of its raw products from China and the other growing markets of the south offers a further opportunity for development for the bulk of African countries. For example, Chinese steel consumption increased by 20% between 1992 and 2002, but the latest data shows that last year 2019 total consumption has increased by 6% which is 875.3million tone, when the world average was 4%. Minerals such as nickel and copper have increased significantly since 2001, vital for the electricity and electronics sectors, The nickel price was 16,255 euro per ton in 2005 on the London spot market compared with 3,725 euro per ton in December 1998. (Lafargue, 2005).

Therefore, African countries have the difficulty of turning this potential benefit into reality. When African States allow Dutch disease syndrome to reoccur, which defined prior booms, then like previous ones, the chance might be rubbed away. If African governments misunderstand the freedom to choose their development paths independently, which means that they will be allowed to continue waste their resources for projects with white elephants and to squander them in external banks, the result will be even more tragic and African developments may be delayed in the very long run. Chances do not occur repeatedly or in rapid successions Finally, the macroeconomic climate can be enhanced by Chinese imports, especially in tiny African countries. Cheap imports of consumer goods prominently inflationary pressures can help reduce consumer spending. It can also help increase income inflows when the overall import volume is increased. It is also true that income generated by imports, directly and/or indirectly, and *ceteris paribus*, will lead to an improvement in the fiscal position of the Government.

5. Conclusion

This research showed that numerous parallels exist in East African Communities between Chinese traders. Many enter on tourist visas, with no needed work licenses or employment permits after arrival. The majority of merchants simply employ tiny staff and have modest investment levels. China's traders are accused of competing with local companies in most African countries. On the other side, the Chinese dealers say that they also help the local economy. They provide accessible items that allow more Africans to access things like consumer electronics or mobile telephones. While local people may grumble that certain Chinese item are of low quality, access to them is beneficial beyond direct sales income. Consumer gadgets and mobile phones enable information access and ease communication, key components for farmers, merchants and businesspeople alike to improve company performance. Immigration corruption impedes the efficiency of immigration regulations meant to safeguard indigenous traders. If such an approach to rents persists, it would not only continue to affect indigenous entrepreneurs, but Chinese traders will also fail

to make long-term investments because of perceived volatility and corrupt investment atmosphere. opting to maximize short-term earnings before migrating to more beautiful nations. Our investigation showed that some ex-Chinese trading partners in Uganda, Kenya, and Tanzania have become some of the largest Chinese firms. They invest significant amounts of money, generate high turnover, and offer a wide range of job possibilities. In designing and implementing policies, the Government should be careful in balancing the interests of its local companies with the contribution of Chinese investors to socio-economic growth.

East Africa's leaders are no longer just opening up their arms to Chinese commerce and investment, but are actively negotiating trade and investment. The report showed that in Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania policies are being implemented in certain sectors and groups of Chinese players such as revisions in Uganda's immigration policy and a harsher implementation of that policy.

KAYNAKÇA

- Kaplinsky, R., D. McCormick and M. Morris (2007), *The Impact of China on Sub Saharan Africa, Working Paper 291*, Institute of Development Studies, University of Sussex, Brighton.
- Alden, C., (2009). *China in Africa*. Zed books Ltd, London/New York
- Kusimba, C. M. 1999. *The Rise and Fall of Swahili states*. Walnut Creek: AltaMira Press.
- Ali D, Bowen D, Deininger K and Duponchel M (2016). *Investigating the Gender Gap in Agricultural Productivity: Evidence from Uganda*. World Development.
- Kusimba, C.M., K. Nam, and SB. Kusimba. (2017). *Trade and State Formation on the Ancient East African and Southern Zambezia' In Feast, Famine or Fighting? Multiple Pathways to Social Complexity*, edited by R.J. Chacon and R. G. Mendoza. Springer, New York.
- Pere, G., (2013). *China in Africa: mercantilist predator, or partner in development?*. Institute for Global Dialogue Midrand, South Africa.
- Lange, G. M., Q. Wodon, and K. Carey. (2018). *The Changing Wealth of Nations 2018: Sustainability into the 21st Century*. Washington: The World Bank.
- Onagoruwa, A., and Q. Wodon (2018). *Measuring the Impact of Child Marriage on Total Fertility: A Study for Fifteen Countries, Journal of Biosocial Science*.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) (2016b). *Assessing Regional Integration in Africa (ARIAVII): Innovation, Competitiveness and Regional Integration*.
- African Development Bank (AfDB). 2014. *The African Development Bank (AfDB), A Partner of Choice for the Eastern Africa We Want*. Nairobi: AfDB East Africa Regional Resource Centre (EARC).
- Pearson, M. N. (2009). *Port Cities and Intruders: The Swahili Coast, India, and Portugal in the Early Modern Era*. Baltimore, MD.: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Sun, Yun. (2014). *Africa in china's foreign policy*. The Brookings Institution.N.p., 14 Apr. Web <<http://www.brookings.edu/research/papers/2014/04/10-africa-china-foreignpolicy- sun>>.
- Sun W.(2017). *China dispatches 2,609 policemen for UN peacekeeping missions, most among permanent members*". People's Daily Online. 25 September 2017. <<http://en.people.cn/n3/2017/0925/c90000-9273387.html>> Accessed 8 May 2020.
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/uganda/gdp>
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/tanzania/gdp>
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/kenya/gdp>
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/kenya/imports/china>
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/tanzania/imports/china>
- <https://tradingeconomics.com/uganda/imports/china>